

RI4C2
Research & Innovation
For Cities & Citizens

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RI4C2 Sessions M6- M12

Report

DELIVERABLE 8.1
MONTH 18

D8.1 – RI4C2 Sessions

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I. Context of the deliverable

A. RI4C2 Sessions

The “Research & Innovation For Cities & Citizens – RI4C2” project aims to extend the activities of the EC2U Alliance to the Research and Innovation fields. The RI4C2 Management Committee (MaCo), the primary governance body, decided to present specific RI4C2 sessions during each EC2U Forum. As presented in the proposal, this session must give a general overview of the project, present the results, and provide key facts and figures on the Partner universities within the Alliance. This session aims to strengthen the links between the two projects and highlight potential collaborations.

B. Overlap of the dates with the Erasmus + project and the SwafS Project

The EC2U Alliance submitted the SwafS project RI4C2 in 2020, and it is directly linked to the Erasmus+ project EC2U (N°101004065). This Erasmus+ project started on 16th October 2020, i.e., one year before the SwafS project. The dates of the Fora have been fixed progressively according to the agenda of all the EC2U partners, observing 6-month interval between fora. However, the Fora had to be shifted by a few months. For this reason, RI4C2 sessions may be conducted with a slight time difference from the dates foreseen in the proposal. In the present deliverable, two RI4C2 sessions will be presented. Those sessions correspond to the sessions of February 2022 (Month 6) and September 2022 (Month 12). The deliverable will be updated at the end of May 2023 since the next session corresponding to Month 18 will take place in mid-May. The third session will take place on 25th May 2023 during the 6th Forum in Jena (Germany).

C. Key speakers

Prof. Dr. Ludovic Thilly

General Coordinator of the EC2U Alliance, University of Poitiers

Ludovic Thilly is Full Professor at the University of Poitiers. Since 2012, he has been Executive Vice-Rector in charge of European Networks. Member of the Executive Board of the Coimbra Group since 2015, he was elected Chair in June 2017 and re-elected in June 2020 for four years.

Chairman of the Executive Board of Coimbra Group.

Ludovic Thilly is a Physicist and works on the deformation mechanisms of (nano-)materials. He has co-authored 70+ publications in international peer-reviewed journals (incl. 4 book chapters) and given 50+ invited lectures at international conferences and institutions.

Professor Thilly is Coordinator of the EC2U European University Alliance and coordinates the informal group of the 24 newly selected Alliances.

Daniela Ovadia, University of Pavia
Co-director Neuroscience and Society Lab

She is a science journalist, neuroscientist and neuroethicist and the Co-director of the Neuroscience and Society Lab at University of Pavia and the Director of the Center for Ethics in Science and Journalism (CESJ) in Milan. She teaches Forensic Neuropsychology, Ethics of Research and Communication of Neurosciences at University of Pavia, SISSA – International School for Advanced Studies in Trieste, University Sapienza in Rome and University San Raffaele in Milan. She is a consultant for the UNESCO Office in Venice and held courses on the ethics in science communication at the Balkan School for Science Journalism (Belgrade, Podgorica).

She is a member of the European Association for Neuroscience and Law, the International Neuroethics Society (INS) and Science Writers in Italy (SWIM).

Her research activity is focused mainly on the social impact of science and research and the ethics of research, with a special interest on the social impact of neuroscience and the role of media in shaping the public perception of science and new technologies. She was one of the WP leaders of the FP7 SATORI Project (Stakeholders Acting Together On the -ethical impact assessment of Research and Innovation) and she coordinated the ethical and legal work package of the Horizon 2020 PROTON project, aimed at improving existing knowledge on the processes of recruitment to organised crime and terrorist networks through an innovative integration between social and computational sciences. She is part of the EC2U-WP3 staff at University of Pavia and the WP leader of WP4 in the RI4C2 project.

Prof. Dr. Raúl Sánchez Prieto, University of Salamanca

Full Professor of German and Dutch Linguistics since 2008 and currently Director of the Department of Modern Philology. Research activity focused on the contrastive linguistics of Spanish and German (and Dutch).

Professor of German and Dutch philology since 2008 and director of the Institute of Modern Philology since 2020. Area of research: contrastive linguistics in the German-Spanish linguistic space (and linguistic contrast).

Professor of German and Dutch linguistics and, since 2020, director of the Department of Modern Philology. Research focuses on German-Spanish contrastive linguistics and language contact.

Daniela Soitu, Alexandru Ioan Cuza University of Iasi

Specialist in social sciences, PhD supervisor in the field of Social Work (since 2019); Dissertation: The person in society. Contexts and resources for development and research in social work (2018). Professor in the Department of Sociology and Social Work of the Faculty of Philosophy and Social- Political Sciences, Alexandru Ioan Cuza University of Iași. PhD Thesis: Specific forms of intervention in social protection of the elderly in the field of Sociology (2004). International experience of training- research;

Developed courses for the disciplines: Counselling in Social Work, Social Work for the Elderly, Negotiation and Conflict Mediation in Social Work, Social Work System, Counselling and Career Guidance (degree level: undergraduate) and Counselling for Personal Development, Alternative Dispute Resolution Strategies, Contextual Dispute Mediation, Victim-Offender Mediation, Areas of

Christian Charity, The Elderly Family, Couples Counselling, Life Skills, Life Course Approach and Lifelong Well- being (for Masters programmes).

Editor in chief: Scientific Annals of Alexandru Ioan Cuza University of Iasi. Sociology and Social Work Section (since 2008-);

Coordinator of the Practical Academy Collection, Alexandru Ioan Cuza University of Iasi Publishing House. Coordinator and expert in international and national research and development projects.

Dana Strauss, University of Jena
Head of office of the regional network JenaVersum

Dana Strauss works as the head of office of the regional network JenaVersum at the University of Jena. She is responsible for coordinating the collaborative platform in order to strengthen the dialogue between research institutions, the city, and businesses. Dana received her doctoral degree in social geography.

Claudia Cavadas, University of Coimbra
Director of the Institute for Interdisciplinary Research

Cavadas holds a PhD in Pharmacology from the Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Coimbra (2002). Since 2002, she is professor at the Faculty of Pharmacy of the University of Coimbra and Group Leader of "Neuroendocrinology and Aging group" at Center for Neuroscience and Cell Biology, University of Coimbra. Cláudia Cavadas is co-author of 80 international publications and was the principal investigator of several funded projects. She was the President of the Portuguese Society of Pharmacology (since 2016); and Vice-director of the Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Coimbra (2011-2013). As a PhD student, Claudia Cavadas spent 3 years at the Division of Hypertension CHUV, Lausanne, Switzerland.

Mangalagiu Ionel, Alexandru Ioan Cuza University of Iași,
Vice-Rector of Research

Dr. Mangalagiu is a professor of organic and medicinal chemistry and Vice-Rector with research at the Alexandru Ioan Cuza University of Iasi, Romania. Previously, prof. Mangalagiu served as Dean, Vice-Dean, Head of Organic Chemistry Department, etc. at Faculty of Chemistry. He has nearly 30 years of experience in the research, focused on the area of Heterocycles Compounds. He has over 150 papers, 15 patents, 3 international chapter books, etc. He was Visiting Professor and/or invited speaker to prestigious foreign universities (Ludwig Maximilian University Munchen and Technische Universität Braunschweig, University of Florence, Université D'Angers, Université Paris Sud), awarded with numerous prizes and honors: DAAD and NATO award, "Costin D. Nenitescu Medal" (Romanian Society of Chemistry), "A.I.Cuza University Award in Research", "Grand Prize Euroinvent" (Euroinvent, Romania), Special Award of Croatian Association of Inventors, etc

Mari Riipinen, University of Turku
Head of Unit, Research Development and Administration

Mari Riipinen is head of unit that is responsible for developing the framework conditions for research at the University of Turku, Finland. The responsibilities are for example Open Science, research ethics, research infrastructures, Cris-system, and multidisciplinary thematic collaborations for research and education. I also have more than 10 years of experience in research funding services.

Before my career in research administration, she did PhD in human geography. Her research topics were in the fields of political ecology, land use, and social capital theory.

II. RI4C2 Session - EC2U Forum N°4 Pavia (Italy)

Agenda of the RI4C2 Session

4th EC2U Forum

Roundtable: “Research & Innovation for cities & citizens” in partnership with RI4C2 project

**7 April 2022
14.30-16.30 CET**

**University of Pavia – Aula Magna
and online¹**

Moderator: L. Thilly (EC2U General Coordinator)	
<p>14.30 – 15:10 [5 minutes each]</p>	<p>RI4C2: An Horizon Europe project for the development of an EC2U Research and Innovation A description of the project aim and structure. Intervention of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - L. Thilly, EC2U and RI4C2 General Coordinator and WP1 Leader : general introduction to RI4c2 and WP1 “Transformation management” scope and planning - R. Sánchez, WP2 Leader: WP2 “EC2U R&I agenda” scope and planning - C. Cavadas, WP3 Leader: WP3 “EC2U People empowerment” scope and planning. - D. Ovadia, WP4 Leader: WP4 “EC2U R&I platforms”, - D. Strauss, WP5 Leader. WP5 “EC2U innovation sphere” - I. Mangalagiu, WP6 Leader: WP6 EC2U Knowledge ecosystems”. - M. Riipinen, WP7 Leader: WP7 Open EC2U. - L. Thilly, WP8 Leader. WP8 “Transformation dissemination”.

¹Live streaming on the [EC2U Youtube channel](#)

Moderator: D. Ovadia (RI4C2 WP leader for University of Pavia)

15.10 - 16:10
[7 minutes each]

Roundtable: "Universities at the core of the knowledge ecosystems"

Intervention of:

- L. Thilly, WP1 Leader. An alliance is also a cultural hub for the academic community and beyond. What is the role of an academic alliance in shaping the future of the European high education landmark?
- R. Sánchez, WP2 Leader: How do we plan to identify new common areas of interest that could lead to common research institutes? What is the role of a Virtual Research Institute in harmonizing research practices and goals? How can a consortium overcome the problem of multilinguism?
- C. Cavadas, WP3. What is the Human Resources Strategy for Researchers (HSR4R) and what can an alliance do to support it? What is, according to the project, the role of an alliance in promoting the career of the young scientists and which are the main barriers?
- D. Ovadia, WP4 Leader: How can a common digital platform help to overcome the issues related to common policing among academic institutions on sensitive issues like gender equality, researchers' behaviors, common procedures and open science?
- D. Strauss, WP5 Leader. How do we promote the values of the academic world through the alliances? How can research and innovation move to the heart of a city?
- I. Mangalagiu, WP6 Leader: What is a knowledge ecosystem, from where we take this concept and how it applies to the universities? How can we involve the citizens in the production of science and why it's important for the quality of our research?
- M. Riipinen, WP7 Leader. What is the role of open science in opening the academic world to the city and the citizens? How do you plan to promote the OA model within your community?
- L. Thilly, WP8 Leader. An alliance is also a cultural hub for the academic community and beyond, especially when we tackle issues like the SDGs. What is our role in disseminating the scientific basis of the SDGs?

Speakers

This session was moderated by Prof. Dr. Daniela Ovidia, this session included the following speakers:

- **Prof. Dr. Ludovic Thilly** (University of Poitiers)
Leader of WP1 “Transformation management” and WP8 “Transformation dissemination”
- **Prof. Dr. Raul Sánchez Prieto** (University of Salamanca)
WP2 Leader: WP2 “EC2U R&I agenda”
- **Prof. Dr. Claudia Cavadas** (University of Coimbra)
WP3 Leader: WP3 “EC2U People empowerment”
- **Prof. Dr. Daniela Ovidia** (University of Pavia)
WP4 Leader: WP4 “EC2U R&I platforms”
- **Dr. Dana Strauss** (University of Jena)
WP5 Leader: WP5 “EC2U innovation sphere”
- **Dr. Daniela Soitu** (University of Iasi)
WP6 Co-leader: WP6 “EC2U Knowledge ecosystems”
- **Dr. Mari Riipinen** (University of Turku)
WP7 Leader: WP7 “Open EC2U”

Description of the session

This session took place from 11:30am to 12:45pm in Aula 400, at the University of Pavia and was livestreamed on the EC2U YouTube channel. The session was organised in partnership with the “Research & Innovation for Cities & Citizens – RI4C2” project, which involves the EC2U Partner Universities. The aim of this session was to share insight on the RI4C2 project and discuss the overarching goals of the project – thus, this session was divided into two sections.

Figure 1: Round table on "Research & Innovation for cities & citizens"

1st section: "RI4C2: An Horizon Europe project for the development of an EC2U Research and Innovation"

Moderated by the General Coordinator of the EC2U Alliance and of the RI4C2 project, Ludovic Thilly, this section included the following speakers:

- Ludovic Thilly (University of Poitiers), Leader of WP1 "Transformation management" and WP8 "Transformation dissemination"
- Raul Sánchez (University of Salamanca), WP2 Leader: WP2 "EC2U R&I agenda"
- Claudia Cavadas (University of Coimbra), WP3 Leader: WP3 "EC2U People empowerment"
- Daniela Ovadia (University of Pavia), WP4 Leader: WP4 "EC2U R&I platforms",
- Dana Strauss (University of Jena), WP5 Leader. WP5 "EC2U innovation sphere"
- Ionel Mangalagiu and Daniela Soitu (University of Iasi), WP6 Leader and co-leader: WP6 EC2U Knowledge ecosystems"
- Mari Riipinen and Laura Niemi (University of Turku), WP7 Leader and co-leader: WP7 Open EC2U

2nd section: A talk show on the key topics of the RI4C2 project

After a brief introduction of the structure of each RI4C2 Work Package structure as well as the goals defined by each WP Leader, a talk show on the topics of the RI4C2 project was moderated by Daniela Ovadia, EC2U-WP3 staff at University of Pavia and the WP leader of WP4 in the RI4C2 project.

Key topics included, but were not limited to:

- what is a knowledge ecosystem?
- how we can engage the stakeholders in the production of knowledge?
- how we can evaluate the research needs of our community?
- how we can use the digital environment and new technologies to work together and to develop tools for the co-creation of policy documents?

The general public (mostly students and members of the academic world) interacted with the speakers and participants, asking questions as well as expressing opinions and suggestions on the future development of the project.

Figure 2: Panel of speakers & overview of the conference room

Dissemination of the session

1. Visual used on social media

2. Graphic recording of the session

Figure 3: Graphic recording by Blanche Illustrates

3. Video on the EC2U YouTube channel

This session is available on the [EC2U YouTube channel](#).

III. RI4C2 Session - EC2U Forum N°5 Iase (Rumania)

Agenda of the RI4C2 Session

European Campus
of City-Universities

Co-funded by the
Erasmus+ Programme
of the European Union

5th EC2U Forum

RI4C2 Session "Research & Innovation for cities & citizens"

12 October 2022
16.30-18.00 Local Time

University Alexandru Ioan Cuza - Aula Magna
and online¹

Moderator: Prof. Dr. Ionel Mangalagiu	
16.30 – 16:35	RI4C2: a Swafs project for the development of Reserach and Innovation ecosystems ("Project outline") Intervention of: - L. Thilly , EC2U General Coordinator
Moderator: Prof. Dr. Ionel Mangalagiu	
16.35 – 17:05	Presentation of the Work Packages results Intervention of: WP2: R&I Needs Prof. Dr. Raúl Sánchez (Head of the Department of Modern Philology, University of Salamanca) Jorge Hernández (EC2U Communication Officer, University of Salamanca) WP3: The HRS4R Label for all the partners Prof. Dr. Claudia Cavadas (Vice-rector and Director of the Institute for Interdisciplinary Research of the University of Coimbra)

¹Live streaming on the EC2U Youtube channel

Co-funded by the
Erasmus+ Programme
of the European Union

	<p>WP4: Digital infrastructure Prof. Dr. Daniela Ovidia (Co-director of the Neuroscience and Society Lab Brain and Behavioral Sciences Dept. - University of Pavia)</p> <p>WP5: Lighthouses of Innovation Dr. Dana Strauss (Regional Network Jena Versum, University of Jena)</p> <p>WP6: Champions on Citizen Science Prof. Dr. Ionel Mangalagiu (Vice-rector for Scientific research programs and Knowledge Transfer, "Alexandru Ioan Cuza" University of Iasi); Prof. Ph.D Daniela Soitu "Alexandru Ioan Cuza" University of Iasi, Department of Sociology and Social Work)</p> <p>WP7: Open Science practices (online) Ph.D. Laura Niemi (Development Specialist, University of Turku)</p>
<p>Moderator: Prof. Dr. Ionel Mangalagiu</p>	
<p>17:05 – 18:00</p>	<p>Discussion with the public on two topics: Gender Equality & Knowledge ecosystem</p> <p>Intervention of:</p> <p>Gender equality panel:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Claudia Cavadas (Vice-rector and Director of the Institute for Interdisciplinary Research of the University of Coimbra) • Daniela Ovidia (Co-director of the Neuroscience and Society Lab Brain and Behavioral Sciences Dept. - University of Pavia) • Dr. Eva Schmucker-Drabe (Institute for German as a Foreign and Second Language and Intercultural Studies, University of Jena) <p>Knowledge Ecosystem panel:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prof. Dr. Ionel Mangalagiu (Vice-rector for Scientific research programs and Knowledge Transfer, "Alexandru Ioan Cuza" University of Iasi) • Prof. Ph.D Daniela Soitu, Department of Sociology and Social Work, "Alexandru Ioan Cuza" University of Iasi • Dr. Dana Strauss (Managing Director Network Jena Versum, University of Jena) • Prof. Dr. Raul Sanches (Head of the Department of Modern Philology, University of Salamanca)

Speakers

This session was moderated by Prof. Dr. Ionel Mangalagiu, this session included the following speakers:

- **Prof. Dr. Ludovic Thilly** (University of Poitiers)
Leader of WP1 “Transformation management” and WP8 “Transformation dissemination”
- **Prof. Dr. Raul Sánchez Prieto** (University of Salamanca)
WP2 Leader: WP2 “EC2U R&I agenda”
- **Jorge Hernandez** (University of Salamanca)
WP2 Local Coordinator
- **Prof. Dr. Claudia Cavadas** (University of Coimbra)
WP3 Leader: WP3 “EC2U People empowerment”
- **Prof. Dr. Daniela Ovadia** (University of Pavia)
WP4 Leader: WP4 “EC2U R&I platforms”
- **Dr. Dana Strauss** (University of Jena)
WP5 Leader: WP5 “EC2U innovation sphere”
- **Dr. Eva Schmucker-Drabe** (University of Jena)
Specialist at the Institute for German as a Foreign and Second Language and Intercultural Studies
- **Dr. Daniela Soitu** (University of Iasi)
WP6 Co-leader: WP6 “EC2U Knowledge ecosystems”
- **Dr. Laura Niemi and Jaakko Kuha** (University of Turku)
WP7 Local coordinator: WP7 “Open EC2U”

Description

This session took place from 4:30pm to 6:45pm in Aula Magna, at the University of Alexandru Ioan Cuza and was livestreamed on the EC2U YouTube channel. The session was organised in partnership with the project Erasmus+, which involves the EC2U Partner Universities. The aim of this session was to share the first RI4C2 results and discuss with the public two main topics that are essential for the project – thus, this session was divided into two sections.

Ludovic Thilly, General Coordinator of the EC2U Alliance and of the Horizon2020 project RI4C2, started the conference with a general overview of the SwafS project for the development of Research and Innovation ecosystems.

Figure 4: RI4C2 Session in Iasi

1st section: “RI4C2: An Horizon Europe project for the development of an EC2U Research and Innovation”

- WP2 “EC2U R&I agenda”: Results from the survey on R&I needs among the seven universities.
- WP3 “EC2U People empowerment”: Roadmap towards HRS4R label for all the partners.
- WP4 “EC2U R&I platforms”: Databases on Research & Innovation
- WP5 “EC2U innovation sphere”: Increasing visibility of our Lighthouses and showcasing best practices.
- WP6 EC2U Knowledge ecosystems”: Identification of Citizen Science champions among the seven universities.
- WP7 Open EC2U: Evaluation & analysis of case descriptions on Open Science.

2nd section: Discussion with the public on Gender Equality & Knowledge ecosystem

The event was conducted as a debate related with two important topics for the project “Gender Equality” and “Knowledge ecosystem” which was moderated by Ionel Mangalagiu and two panels of experts. All along the discussion, online questions were addressed to the audience via Wooclap.

Here below some of the questions discussed with the panel on Gender Equality:

- What is Gender Equality?

- What are the most crucial points of gender inequality in academia/research for you?
- What can we do in our everyday life to reach gender equality in academia/research?
- Do you think gender equality is respected in your university?"

Here below some of the questions and topics discussed with the panel on Knowledge ecosystem:

- Which institutions are involved in the Knowledge Ecosystem: Universities and Research Entities, Innovative start-ups, Local and Regional authorities, Venture capital, sponsors, Service organizations, incumbent firms, Citizen Science entities, others?
- Knowledge Ecosystem actors/entities and the relation between them
- An example of Knowledge ecosystem: Jena Versum
- How are universities involved in the Knowledge Ecosystem?
- How digital technologies may be better implemented in research and innovation activities in: Production, acquisition, organization, transmission, sharing, data collection, none, other"
- Which strategy is better for organising a knowledge ecosystem: moving towards integration or maintaining a segregated and specialised ecosystem?

Figure 5: Session on "Research & Innovation for cities & citizens"

Dissemination of the session

1. Visual used on social media

2. Video on the EC2U YouTube channel

This session is available on the [EC2U YouTube channel](#).

This report reflects only the author's view and does not reflect the opinions of the European Union or the European Commission. The Agency and the European Commission are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.